

Initial Setup Steps

1. Download code from https://github.com/mwang87/GNPS_LibraryDashboard
2. GNPS_LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks\
3. Download all files from Zenodo
4. Open and go to GNPS_LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks\carnitine_notebooks\manuscript_notebooks_final\
5. Download all files from Zenodo
6. Open and go to GNPS_LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks\bile_acid_notebooks\manuscript_notebooks_final\
7. Download all files from Zenodo

Preprocessing Notebooks (GNPS_LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks)

- **clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb**
 - **Purpose** - Clean GNPS Library metadata
 1. Remove spectrum_ids associated with Suspect List data
 2. Isolate spectrum_ids associated with M+H adduct
 - **Input requirements**
 1. GNPS Library metadata from https://gnps-external.ucsd.edu/gnpslibrary/ALL_GNPS.json
 - **Output**
 1. csv of cleaned metadata
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/**CLEANED_GNPS_input_library.csv**
- **v_rdkit_functions.py**
 - **Purpose** - Generate RDKit-related outputs from metadata
 1. Identifies molecules described in input library based on known SMILES in metadata
 2. Returns a subselection of library dataframe for rows containing substructure of interest
- **v_boxplots_manuscript_final_figures_R.Rmd**
 - **Purpose** - Drawing diagnostic peak boxplots
 1. Carnitine boxplot
 2. Dihydroxy BA boxplot
 - **Input requirements**
 1. csv outputs from diagnostic_peaks_carnitine_M+H.ipynb
 2. csv outputs from **diagnostic_peaks_di_BA_M+H.ipynb**
 - **Output**
 1. Carnitine boxplot exported as png
 - Carnitine_boxplot_final_fig.png (**Figure 2a**)
 2. Dihydroxy BA boxplot exported as png
 - bileacid_boxplot_final_fig.png (**Figure 2b**)

Carnitine Notebooks (GNPS LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks\carnitine_notebooks\manuscript_notebooks_final\)

- shape_carnitine_msql_output.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - Clean MassQL output (using cleaned GNPS Library data)
 1. Remove spectrum_ids associated with Suspect List data
 2. Isolate spectrum_ids associated with M+H adduct
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Data exported from <https://msql.ucsd.edu/> related to carnitine MassQL query
 2. Cleaned GNPS Library metadata from clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb
 - **Output**
 - csv of cleaned MassQL data
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/massql_carnitine_query_peaks_nl_output_matched_for_venn_diagram.csv
- annotation_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - Identifying carnitine compounds in GNPS Library by manual annotation/explicit mention of “carnitine” in compound name
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Cleaned GNPS Library metadata from clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb
 - **Output**
 1. csv of GNPS Library data that describe carnitines (M+H adduct) identified by annotation
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/library_df_carnitine_case_insen_M+H.csv
- substructure_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - Identifying carnitine compounds in GNPS Library by SMILES substructure
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Cleaned GNPS Library metadata from clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb
 - **Output**
 1. csv of GNPS Library data that describe carnitines (M+H adduct) identified by substructure
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/library_df_w_carnitine_substruc.csv
- diagnostic_peaks_carnitine_M+H.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - identify diagnostic fragmentation peaks
 - **Input requirements**
 1. MS/MS peak data (from v_get_peaks_files.ipynb → reads feather files)
 2. Dataframe output of carnitine metadata in GNPS Library from annotation_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 - **Output**
 1. csv of filtered MS/MS peak data
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/carnitine_notebooks/files_for_box_plot/filtered_peak_df_carnitines_M+H.csv

2. csv of consistent fragmentation peaks by descending percent occurrence
 - /home/jovyan/work/notebooks/carnitine_notebooks/files_for_box plot/peak_ratio_df_carnitines_M+H.csv
- diagnostic_neutral_loss_carnitine_M+H.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - identify consistent neutral losses
 - **Input requirements**
 1. MS/MS peak data (from v_get_peaks_files.ipynb → reads feather files)
 2. Dataframe output of carnitine metadata in GNPS Library from annotation_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 - **Output**
 1. Table of neutral losses by percent occurrence
- massql_query_assessment_carnitine_M+H.ipynb
 - **Purpose** - Assessing the MassQL query success of identifying carnitine structures
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Dataframe output of carnitine metadata in GNPS Library from substructure_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 2. Dataframe output of carnitine metadata in GNPS Library from annotation_search_identify_carnitine.ipynb
 3. Cleaned MassQL query output from shape_carnitine_msq_output.ipynb
 - **Important sections**
 - **Section 3:** Unique structures in annotation-identified carnitine data
 1. **Output**
 - USI link for MS/MS identified by library annotation without structural metadata (**SI Data 6**)
 - **Section 5:** Venn Diagram - unique structures identified by MassQL vs annotation search
 1. **Output**
 - Venn diagram (Main Manuscript **Figure 3a**)
 - **Section 6:** Venn Diagram - MS/MS identified by MassQL vs annotation search
 1. **Output**
 - Venn diagram (**SI Figure 1a**)
 - **End of Section 7**
 1. **Output**
 - USI link for MS/MS identified by MassQL query and library annotation (**SI Data 3**)
 - **Section 8:** Venn Diagram - unique structures identified by annotation vs substructure search
 1. **Output**
 - Venn diagram (**SI Figure 1b**)
 - **End of Section 9**
 1. **Output**

- USI link for MS/MS identified by library annotation and substructure search (**SI Data 4**)
 - USI link for MS/MS exclusively identified by library annotation and not substructure search (**SI Data 5**)
- **Section 10:** Inner structures captured by MassQL and annotation search
 1. **Output**
 - RDKit drawn structures (**SI Figure 2a**)
- **Section 11:** Outer structures only captured by annotation search
 1. **Output**
 - RDKit drawn structures (**SI Figure 2b**)

Dihydroxy Bile Acid Notebooks (GNPS LibraryDashboard-master\notebooks\bile_acid_notebooks\manuscript_notebooks_final\)

- **shape_di_BA_msql_output.ipynb**
 - **Purpose** - Clean MassQL output (using cleaned GNPS Library data)
 1. Remove spectrum_ids associated with Suspect List data
 2. Isolate spectrum_ids associated with M+H adduct
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Data exported from <https://msql.ucsd.edu/> related to dihydroxy BA MassQL query
 2. Cleaned GNPS Library metadata from **clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb**
 - **Output**
 1. csv of cleaned MassQL data
 - **/home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/massql_all_di_query_peaks_nl_output_matched_for_venn_diagram.csv**
- **substructure_search_identify_di_BA.ipynb**
 - **Purpose** - Identifying dihydroxy BA compounds in GNPS Library by SMILES substructure
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Cleaned GNPS Library metadata from **clean_GNPS_Library_data.ipynb**
 - **Output**
 1. csv of GNPS Library data that describe dihydroxy BA (M+H adduct) identified by substructure
 - **/home/jovyan/work/notebooks/outputs/library_df_dihydroxy_BA_only_m+h_updated_matches.csv**
- **diagnostic_peaks_di_BA_M+H.ipynb**
 - **Purpose** - identify diagnostic fragmentation peaks
 - **Input requirements**
 1. MS/MS peak data (from **v_get_peaks_files.ipynb** → reads feather files)
 2. Dataframe output of dihydroxy-BA metadata in GNPS Library from **substructure_search_identify_di_BA.ipynb**
 - **Output**
 1. csv of filtered MS/MS peak data
 - **/home/jovyan/work/notebooks/bile_acid_notebooks/files_for_box_plot/filtered_peak_df_BA_di_3_7_M+H.csv**
 2. csv of consistent fragmentation peaks by descending percent occurrence
 - **/home/jovyan/work/notebooks/bile_acid_notebooks/files_for_box_plot/peak_ratio_df_BA_di_3_7_M+H.csv**
- **diagnostic_neutral_loss_di_BA_M+H.ipynb**
 - **Purpose** - identify consistent neutral losses
 - **Input requirements**
 1. MS/MS peak data (from **v_get_peaks_files.ipynb** → reads feather files)
 2. Dataframe output of dihydroxy-BA metadata in GNPS Library from **substructure_search_identify_di_BA.ipynb**

- **Output**
 1. Table of neutral losses by descending percent occurrence
- [massql_query_assessment_di_BA_M+H.ipynb](#)
 - **Purpose** - Assessing the MassQL query success of identifying dihydroxy BA structures
 - **Input requirements**
 1. Dataframe output of dihydroxy-BA metadata in GNPS Library from [substructure_search_identify_di_BA.ipynb](#)
 2. Cleaned MassQL query output from [shape_di_BA_msq_output.ipynb](#)
 - **Important sections**
 - **Section 4:** Inner structures captured by BOTH sets
 1. **Output**
 - RDKit drawn structures (**SI Figure 8**)
 - **Section 5:** Outer structures ONLY captured by MassQL query
 1. **Output**
 - RDKit drawn structures (**SI Figure 6**)
 - **Section 6:** Outer structures ONLY captured by substructure search
 1. **Output**
 - RDKit drawn structures (**SI Figure 7**)
 - **Section 7:** Venn Diagram
 1. **Output**
 - Venn diagram (Main Manuscript **Figure 4a**)
 - USI link for MS/MS identified by MassQL query and substructure (**SI Data 9**)
 - USI link for MS/MS exclusively identified by substructure (**SI Data 8**)
 - USI link for MS/MS exclusively identified by MassQL query (**SI Data 7**)
 - **Section 8:** Barplots
 1. **Output (SI Figure 5)**
 - Barplot showing structure counts exclusively identified by MassQL (**SI Figure 5b**)
 - Barplot showing structure counts exclusively identified by substructure search (a.k.a. structures missed by MassQL) (**SI Figure 5c**)
 - Barplot showing structure counts identified by both searches (**SI Figure 5a**)